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SMARTCHAIN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The general aim of the **SMARTCHAIN** project is to develop approaches and tools for sustainable utilisation, production planning, logistics optimisation, and traceability to facilitate sustainable transformation and circularity of bio-resources from catch/production throughout the value chain of fisheries and aquaculture products.

WP3 Sustainable resource use and circularity has three main tasks. In T3.1 the aim was to *specify sustainability indicators that can be used to assess blue bioeconomy activities* in general and more specifically for the fisheries and aquaculture sectors which are the primary focus of the SMARTCHAIN project's case studies. In T3.2 *Stakeholder engagement* the aim was to engage stakeholders for consultation on the selected indicators from T3.1 and assess their willingness to share data and assessment results for enhanced transparency and circularity. As companies are already reporting their sustainability performance and utilising common frameworks and established indicators in their CSR reports in line with the selected set of indicators reported in D3.1, the approach for the stakeholder activities was revised towards in-depth interviews and focus groups rather than workshops.

SMARTCHAIN explores the perceptions of companies, experts and policy makers in Iceland and Norway to gauge the ways in which they contribute to the circular bioeconomy. The goal is to elucidate the opportunities and challenges for advancement of circular blue bioeconomy strategies.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the stakeholder engagement activity was to conduct in-depth interviews and focus groups to gauge the view of stakeholders in Iceland and Norway on the challenges involved in transforming the fisheries and aquaculture food supply systems towards more sustainable and circular bioeconomic systems. The goal was to identify the stakeholders' perception on the drivers and barriers regarding transformation of the food system as well as assessing synergies and trade-off.

KEY OUTCOME

Previous work on mapping and indicator selection in the SMARTCHAIN project is summarised herein and aligned to a conceptual circular bioeconomy framework to visualise hotspots and underpin the interpretation of the findings from the multistakeholder interviews and focus groups. The findings on drivers and barriers for implementing sustainability and circularity in the blue bioeconomy were categorised according to key themes: regulatory, resource, market and social, focusing on the sustainability dimensions and probing further on circularity and governance more broadly. The need for improved documentation of rest raw material and waste and a holistic food system assessment was identified in both countries. A lack of infrastructure and a need for policy integration was discussed in Iceland while taxation was an issue of concern in Norway. The detailed results will be published in a scientific journal.

NEXT STEPS

Continued work will be on exploring multistakeholder processes and governance aspects of aquaculture and fisheries supply chains with the aim to promote improvements for circular business models and guide policy making. The aim of T3.3 is to identify the key leverage points and role of actors in different scenarios in the blue bioeconomy supply chain with a focus on circularity and innovation towards sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR CIRCULAR BLUE BIOECONOMY

The blue bioeconomy needs to follow the principles of sustainable development such that it contributes to meeting the needs of present generations without compromising the needs of future generations through a focus on the three main pillars of sustainability: economic, social, and environmental, and including governance (Fritsche et al., 2020). SMARTCHAIN focuses on circular economy solutions for the blue bioeconomy. Blue bioeconomy development can support the achievement of broad societal goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through an emphasis on sustainability, circularity, and innovative approaches. A conceptual framework is applied here to visualise the circularity in blue bioeconomy systems (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Conceptual framework for the circular bioeconomy (Carus 2017) adapted to aquaculture and fisheries as examples of blue bioeconomy systems.

The blue bioeconomy emphasizes aquatic or marine environments, and involves a specific focus on novel applications, including non-food, food, and feed. The blue bioeconomy includes both primary and secondary activities and other sectors may be connected to the blue bioeconomy through their services to bioeconomic activities (Nordic Council, 2014).

The bioeconomy “is the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy” (COM, 2019, p. 8).

The circular economy (CE) is a way to increase resource efficiency by intentionally narrowing, slowing, and closing materials and energy flows. In the context of bioeconomy, we refer to cascading which is a way to use raw materials in chronologically sequential steps as long, often, and efficiently as possible and only to recover energy from them at the end of the product life cycle. Cascading use of biomass takes place when biomass is processed into a biobased final product and this final product is used at least once more either for materials or energy. When biomass is used directly for energy production that’s not cascading use (Figure 1).

The circular economy paradigm calls for the redesign of a linear economic system to a circular system based on closed-loop resource flows.

Research in recent years has been centred on the awareness and definitions of the terms bioeconomy and circular economy (CE), which varies across countries and depends on the diverse role of stakeholders in different disciplines. There is in general a lack of common understanding of the concepts, criteria, indicators, and metrics to assess the circular economy performance of both regions and organizations (Oanh Thi-Kieu Ho et al., 2023¹; Valls Val et al., 2022²).

1.2. RESOURCE UTILISATION AND CIRCULAR BLUE BIOECONOMY

The mapping activities in WP1 identified hotspots in aquaculture and fisheries with respect to challenges of circularity in seafood value chains in Iceland and Norway. Improvements through technological innovation are needed to maintain quality of raw material on board vessels and quality characterisation for better use of resources and minimisation of waste, as well as transformation of co-streams into value added products, along with transparency of information through traceability in the supply chain, (Mehta et al., 2022)³. The results from WP1 on hot spots identification and mapping rest raw materials and food loss and waste in fisheries and aquaculture supply chain were presented at the icRS 2023 (Box1) conference⁴.

Box 1. Can higher resource utilization be achieved in fisheries supply chains? - Status and challenges from Iceland and Norway

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Abstract: Amid a climate, food, and biodiversity crisis, reducing the negative impacts of global fisheries is necessary. Most of the harvested fish from Norway and Iceland is from sustainable, but fully exploited fish stocks. Increasing the harvest is therefore not considered a sustainable option to meet the future demand of seafood protein in a growing population. Simultaneously, there are significant amounts of under-utilised rest raw materials (RRM), such as heads, skins, viscera, and food loss and waste (FLW) occurring in the fisheries supply chain. Increasing resource utilisation has the potential of creating more circular supply chains and meet global sustainability targets such as SDG #12 (Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns), which will contribute to higher value-added products. A holistic view of the fisheries supply chains is needed, including transport, secondary processing, storage, and retail.

We propose a conceptual model of the fisheries supply chain in Norway and Iceland based on material and information flows modelling technique (MIFMT). Here we aim to identify where FLW occur and where there is a potential to increase the use of RRM, and which regulatory, technical, and logistical barriers and opportunities exist for increased sustainability and resource efficiency in fisheries supply chains. Several drivers for FLW in fisheries chains have been identified for example catch technology, communication, over purchase, cold chain inefficiency, packaging, rejection due to quality issues.

Our findings show that regulatory interventions during harvest and improved RRM traceability could improve the use of RRM in fisheries supply chains. Information sharing between the fishing fleet, seafood processors and the marine ingredient sector will allow improved resource utilization through better management of supply and demand. A focus on the retail stage will result in larger savings of FLW which could reduce GHG emissions.

¹ Oanh Thi-Kieu Ho, Akvan Gajanayake, Usha Iyer-Rania,(2023). Transitioning to a state-wide circular economy: Major stakeholder interviews, Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances, 19, 2023, 200163, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2023.200163>

² Valls-Val, K., Ibáñez- Forés, V., Bovea, M.D., 2022. How can organisations measure their level of circularity? A review of available tools. J. Clean. Prod. 354, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131679>

³ Mehta, S., Myhre, M., Olafsdottir, G., Iordan, C.M., Thakur, M. (2022). Resource utilization in seafood supply chains: Food loss, food waste and rest raw materials. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D1.1 &D1.2, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 48 pages

⁴ Andrea Viken Strand, Magnus Stoud Myhre, Shraddha Mehta*, Gudrun Ólafsdóttir, Nina Maria Saviolidis (2023) Can higher resource utilization be achieved in fisheries supply chains? -Status and challenges from Iceland and Norway. icRS 2023 conference August 7-9th 2023, University of Surrey, UK

streams and mortalities was identified in the Horizon 2020 GAIN project⁸. By-products from processing are generally Category 3 ABPs and can be used as feed raw materials, while mortalities are Category 2 ABPs, and their legal uses are mostly restricted and can mainly be utilised for low-value composting or biogas and fuel production. However, self-dead fish may be used as feed ingredients for e.g. fur producing animals. Furthermore, rest raw materials like heads and frames from fish, also being a secondary output in processing, are often slightly prepared (i.e. dried) for human consumption and therefore, not defined as a 'by-product', following the ABP categories and notably liver and roe are traditionally used for human consumption. The Regulation (EC) No. 1069/2009 recognises that progress in science and technology may lead to the development of processes which eliminate or minimise the risks to public and animal health and therefore amendments to the lists of animal by-products set out in this Regulation should be considered⁸.

1.3 INDICATORS FOR THE CIRCULAR BLUE BIOECONOMY

The research in WP3 (T3.1) had the purpose to select framework and indicators for sustainability assessments based on literature review of existing indicators with a focus on the circularity approach for the selected SMARTCHAIN case studies and two selection criteria: a) data availability, b) relevance to different sustainability dimensions (environmental, social, economic, and governance) and relevant goals with the aim to contribute to the SDG goals and Circular Bio Economy Strategies. The indicators were selected through expert consultation with a mix of qualitative and quantitative assessment criteria aligned to established guidelines for indicator selection. A core set of sustainability indicators was identified that can be used to assess circular blue bioeconomy activities in general and more specifically for fisheries and aquaculture. The reporting of the set of indicators which is based on a review of existing indicators with a focus on the circularity approach for the selected SMARTCHAIN case studies and modelling scenarios are reported in SMARTCHAIN deliverable D3.1 (Saviolidis et al., 2022)⁹. The final selection resulted in 35 indicators in the environmental dimension, 14 indicators in the economic dimension, 21 indicators in the social dimension and 20 indicators in the governance dimension. Supplementary sets were also selected which include an additional set of indicators, 11 for harvesting, 22 for processing and 19 for aquaculture.

The sustainability indicators were selected from pre-existing frameworks relevant to the topic of circular blue bioeconomy. The primary framework selected was the European Commission's "Sustainability criteria for the blue economy", which was further cross-referenced with the FAO's "Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy" and the GRI standards.

One major issue with indicator sets is that they tend to be quite demanding in terms of the amount of data that needs to be collected. However, the demand for more detailed data is not likely to reduce in the coming years. Increasingly sophisticated reporting standards such as the GRI and ESG standards, as well as regulation such as the EU directive on non-financial disclosures and the EU taxonomy show that regulators and investors are increasingly more interested in the sustainability aspects of business. Another case in point is the data required by Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) whose 231 unique indicators

⁸ Mohamed Soula, Richard Newton, Carlos Ruiz, Leticia Regueiro, Diego Mendez, Martina Ferreira, Johan Johansen, David Little. Report on legislation, regulation, and certification of aquaculture within the circular economy. 2019. Deliverable 3.1. GAIN - Green Aquaculture Intensification in Europe. EU Horizon 2020 project grant no. 773330. 75 pp.

⁹ SMARTCHAIN Deliverable 3.1: Saviolidis, N.M. and Olafsdottir, G. (2022). Sustainable resource use and circularity: Selected indicators. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF) Deliverable: D3.1, University of Iceland, Reykjavik, 33 pages.

dwarf the 60 indicators by which the previous global Goals (the Millennium Development Goals) were to be measured.

A draft of new European sustainability reporting standards (ESRS) developed by the EFRAG was published in November 2022. These new standards will ensure common reporting approaches for all companies the law applies to which will, in turn, facilitate comparative assessments between companies and across sectors. The ESRS cover Cross cutting standards on General requirements and General disclosures as well as Topical standards in three areas: **1) Environment:** Climate change, pollution, water and marine resources, biodiversity, and circular economy; **2) Social:**

Own workforce, workers in the value chain, affected communities, and customers and end-users; **3) Governance:** Business conduct.

It is expected that ESRS indicators will be published for different sectors and most likely they will be based on earlier established indicators. The advantage of using previously developed indicator sets to monitor progress, is that extensive review work, which has been put into their development, ensures that the indicators chosen are for the most part already being used in some capacity and that the methodology behind them is well-defined.

Sectoral standards, indicators, and methodologies according to e.g., GSI (Global salmon initiative), Global GAP, ASC (Aquaculture Stewardship Council), MSC (Marine Stewardship Council) as well as food processing standards recognised by GFSI (Global Food Safety Initiative) such as BRC, IFS, and feed standards (IFFO, FEMAS) are already implemented in many aquaculture, fisheries, feed and seafood processing companies. These standards and certifications have been instrumental in progressing the performance of companies regarding documentation and reporting of key sustainability issues. It is foreseen that the new European sustainability reporting standards (ESRS) will motivate a common approach for companies and hopefully streamline the documentation required by standards and reporting. However, the establishment of the ESRS indicators will need a multistakeholder approach and collaboration of standard setting bodies, industries, and regulators to ensure implementation and effectiveness of the ESRS standards. The new Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (*Directive (EU) 2022/2464, 2022*) will ensure the compliance of companies to report according to the new ESRS standards. The regulatory requirements may influence that voluntary standards may be less needed in the future, or the question is if they will still be a means of verification of performance for companies while the surveillance and monitoring by the authorities may be fragmented and not efficiently implemented?

It has been emphasised that the transition towards circular bioeconomy requires a holistic approach and all the sustainability dimensions must be included. Figure 3 shows an overview of the SMARTCHAIN indicator selection (from D3.1) for the sustainability dimensions of the circular blue bioeconomy system (fisheries and aquaculture). The criteria established for the indicators were initially based on the COM framework, but it was at the time (in 2022) insufficient to cover fisheries and aquaculture sectors, and therefore, the FAO's "Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy" were added including criteria of fisheries and farm management, and specific criteria for energy efficiency, waste management and wastewater etc.⁹

"The ESRS (European sustainability reporting standards) are a set of new standards and indicators that aim to put an end to reporting practices that follow a plethora of different national framework references or other standards, such as GRI, SDGs and the UN Global Compact, by standardising the way in which companies report on non-financial aspects".

Figure 3 Criteria of indicators selected by SMARTCHAIN D3.1 (Saviolidis et al., 2022)⁹ for the sustainability dimensions of the circular blue bioeconomy system (fisheries and aquaculture)

1.4 CSR REPORTING AND CONTENT ANALYSIS

Corporate sustainability reporting has been mandatory for large, listed companies in the EU since 2016. Norway and Iceland as EEA members have implemented these directives. The EU Non-financial Reporting Directive (NFRD) (*Directive 2014/95/EU*, 2014) has been amended by a new directive, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (*Directive (EU) 2022/2464*, 2022). The CSRD includes a broader set of large companies (listed and unlisted) as well as listed SMEs. The companies subject to the CSRD will have to report according to the newly developed European sustainability reporting standards (ESRS).

Sustainability reports may play an important role as a supporting tool in the transition of organisations towards more circular economy models, since their content can help to measure, monitor, and communicate the organisations' transition and to establish goals in the short/medium term (Ibáñez- Forés et al., 2022)¹⁰. The authors performed content analysis of CSR reports and identified common CE categories considering the life cycle stages of a standard organisation and aspects of the circular economy (Design, Suppliers, Inputs, Production, Business, Outputs, Environmental Impact, Social, R&D in circularity and Communication). The most frequently reported circularity aspects identified were Greenhouse Gas Emissions, followed by the Total Energy Consumed, and Waste Generation.

Companies in the seafood sector have been reporting their sustainability performance in their CSR reports for some years and the reporting is becoming increasingly detailed and more common especially among larger companies. A preliminary analysis of the non-financial reporting of the largest Icelandic fisheries companies according to catch volumes in 2022-2023 showed that sustainability statements and reports have become available on the companies' websites in the last few years in Icelandic, and some are also in English. (See list of companies in Annex V. CSR reporting (Iceland)). The reports are prepared in accordance with the GRI Standard (Global Reporting Initiative GRI100-400) and Fisheries Iceland's and Nasdaq's ESG reporting guide 2.0, which was translated to Icelandic in 2020.

One of the objectives in WP3 is to assess the utility of the selected indicators for circular bioeconomy assessment by exploring the use of sustainability indicators in CSR reports of companies in the fisheries and aquaculture supply chains in Norway and Iceland

Fisheries Iceland¹¹ have established a joint policy of social responsibility based on the UN SDG goals [Responsible Fishing industry \(sfs.is\)](https://www.sfs.is/). According to the SFS's website more than 30 fisheries companies have signed the joint policy among them the largest companies. The companies have put forward sustainability statements in line with the policy on their websites and the CSR reports. The themes from the SDG goals have been adapted and aligned to their activities concerning ways to make improvements. The themes are **Life below water** with a focus on sustainable fisheries and safeguarding the ecosystem by e.g., strengthening research on ocean ecology and marine chemistry and thus improve understanding of the effects of warming and acidification of the sea and plastic pollution on marine life. **Innovation and development**, Environmental dimension is on **Circular economy, minimizing carbon**

¹⁰ Valeria Ibáñez- Forés, Virginia Martínez-Sánchez, Karen Valls-Val, María D. Bovea, (2022). Sustainability reports as a tool for measuring and monitoring the transition towards the circular economy of organisations: Proposal of indicators and metrics (2022). *Journal of Environmental Management*, 320, 2022, 115784, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115784>

¹¹ Fisheries Iceland (SFS) was established in 2014 when the Federation of Icelandic Fishing Vessel Owners and the Federation of Icelandic Fish Processing Plants merged. The association's goal is to safeguard the interests of the fisheries sector, including companies in aquaculture. [Ábyrgur sjávarútvegur \(sfs.is\)](https://www.sfs.is/).

footprint and Energy use and switching to alternative energy sources. Finally, Corporate governance covers **Code of conduct.**

From the list of 15 companies analysed (see ANNEX V), eight have published their sustainability reports on their websites. The environmental indicators used in the companies' reports are on energy/fuel use of the fleet, GHG emissions (a few are reporting Scope 1,2, and 3) and type of waste and recycling (mainly fishing gear). The social aspects cover for example statements on employee rights and gender equality / equal pay. The companies have certifications listed on their websites such as MSC which has been acquired by all the companies who are also members of ISF (Iceland Sustainable Fisheries). IRF (Iceland Responsible Fisheries) verification of origin, is also common, and fisheries involved in pelagic fisheries are certified against IFFO and FEMAS (feed material assurance). Companies involved in processing have implemented standards approved by GFSI (Global Food Safety Initiative) which is also a new requirement (effective in May 2024) along with ASC certification for large companies. Many of the companies are also certified against the Icelandic IST85:2012 gender equality standard on equal pay (see Annex V. CSR reporting (Iceland))

The company Brim has been a pioneer in Iceland regarding transparent reporting on various non-financial indicators according to GRI and ESG guidelines, along with their financial statement since 2017. Brim's sustainability and environmental policy is based on the UN SDG goals in line with the Fisheries Iceland's (SFS) joint policy, but Brim has also formulated its own strategy on environmental and climate issues and set clear goals in relation to social and environmental factors. The focus is on improving circularity (e.g. recycling of waste and reuse and recycling of fishing gear), minimise carbon footprint (e.g. use of more environmentally friendly refrigerants, and enhance energy efficiency and energy transition). The fuel use of the fishing fleet is an ongoing challenge while transition to electricity for the fishmeal production was achieved in Vopnafjörður ten years ago, but there are limitations regarding energy supply. The reporting of Scope 3 emissions regarding transport has been improved by collaboration with suppliers and service companies and sharing of actual data. The carbon footprint of the company's products is calculated according to ISO 22948:2020 (Carbon footprint for seafood). Most of the transport of fresh products is by vessel (85.8%) and only 14.2% of fresh products is transported by air. The content of Brim's annual and sustainability reports is gradually being developed in the last years to prepare for increased requirements for disclosures due to non-financial reporting related to the implementation of CSRD (Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive) and SFDR (Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation). <https://arsskyrsla2022.brim.is/en>.

The upcoming research will explore further policy aimed at facilitating implementation of circularity objectives and the role of governance. The characteristic hybrid governance of the seafood industry is regulated through a combination of public and private governance arrangements, including public regulation, private certification schemes, and self-regulation involving many actors including the state, private businesses, and society (Vince and Hayward¹², Ólafsdóttir et al., 2019¹³, Luthman et al., 2019¹⁴, Rector et al., 2024¹⁵).

¹² Vince J., and Haward M. (2017), Hybrid governance of aquaculture: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Environmental Management* 201 138-144

¹³ Ólafsdóttir, G.; Mehta, S.; Richardsen, R.; Cook, D.; Gudbrandsdóttir, I.Y.; Thakur, M.; Lane, A.; Bogason, S.G. Governance of the farmed salmon Value Chain from Norway to the EU. *Aquac. Eur.* 2019, 44, 5–19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494436>

¹⁴ Luthman, O., Jonell, M., Troell, M. (2019). Governing the salmon farming industry: Comparison between national regulations and the ASC salmon standard. *Marine Policy* 106, 103534 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103534>

¹⁵ Rector, M., Filgueira, R., Grant, J. (2024) The role of salmon aquaculture eco-certification in corporate social responsibility and the delivery of ecosystem services and disservices. *Marine Policy*, 160, February 2024, 105948 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105948>

2. METHODS

INTERVIEWS

Stakeholder identification matrix was used to identify key informants. Recruitment of stakeholders included relevant actors from the seafood supply chain, value-added processes, and relevant suppliers and service providers. Sector experts as well as actors with societal, organisational and governance responsibilities as relevant for the fisheries and aquaculture case studies in Iceland and Norway, were involved. (see [Annex III Concept Note for Interviews](#))

Eighteen in-depth, semi-structured interviews with key informants including 20 participants (2 interviews with 2 participants each) in the blue bioeconomy in Iceland (9) and Norway (8) and EU policy maker (1). Interviewees were from primary industries (fisheries and aquaculture) and secondary/supporting industries including biotech and tech solutions' companies, experts and research institutes and policy makers/public institutions. Additionally, two focus groups were conducted in Iceland with aquaculture companies and experts (see Annex IV Descriptives - Interviews).

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

The data analysis was conducted using the MAXQDA software. The analytical framework applied to analyse the data is based on institutional theory. It consists of four broad categories: Regulatory which includes domestic and international regulations, policies, roadmaps, strategies etc. Resources include both tangible resources like material, financial, physical but also intangible like knowledge and skills. Market involves issues relating to customers, consumers, partners or competitors in the value chain, service providers and industry associations and finally social involves the community at large involving NGOs, local communities, the media, and issues to do with image and reputation and corporate social responsibility and organizational values.

Figure 4 Thematic categorization of drivers and barriers

Source: Saviolidis et al., 2023, adapted from Hoffman, 2000; Chkanikova & Mont, 2012)

REPORTING

Herein is a summary of preliminary findings and literature. A scientific publication is in progress with detailed results from the stakeholder interviews. The preliminary findings on drivers and barriers have already been presented at webinars / conferences. Furthermore, the SMARTCHAIN project will organise webinars in the third year of the project to present the overall findings including the findings on challenges and enablers such as policy gaps and recommendations on policy integration and strategies to facilitate the transition to circular blue bioeconomy.

3. RESULTS

3.1 DRIVERS AND BARRIERS FOR IMPLEMENTING CIRCULARITY IN THE BLUE BIOECONOMY – PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

Preliminary findings from stakeholder focus groups and interviews on the drivers and barriers for implementing circularity were presented at NKJ webinar¹⁶ and the icRS 2023 conference¹⁷ as detailed in the abstract see Box 2 below.

Box 2. Drivers and barriers for the advancement of a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland and Norway

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Abstract: A circular bioeconomy can reduce dependence on non-renewable resources, promote sustainable resource use, and support the development of innovative bio-based products and services. The blue bioeconomy (i.e., aquatic resources) is an under researched but integral part of the bioeconomy especially in nations such as Iceland and Norway with economically significant blue industries (e.g., fisheries and aquaculture).

The circular economy paradigm calls for the redesign of the linear economic system whereby the environmental and social costs of products are externalized, to a circular system based on closed-loop resource flows that can preserve the embedded environmental and economic value in products over time. In-depth interviews and focus groups with key stakeholders - high level managers, industry (primary, secondary, and supporting), and government and industry experts - were conducted in Iceland and Norway to investigate the major institutional factors for the advancement of a more circular and sustainable blue bioeconomy.

The analysis was supplemented and triangulated by review of regional and national policy and strategy documents. The findings show that realising the potential of a more circular blue bioeconomy requires the development of target-based overarching strategies and the implementation of a systemic approach cutting across different sectors (e.g., agriculture, tourism, transport, and energy sector).

Companies need to reconsider their value creation and adopt strategies that promote circular economy objectives for the biobased sector including increased collaboration through clusters and public-private partnerships. Overcoming barriers such as the lack of institutional and infrastructural capacity requires the attention of policymakers and investors.

Advancing a more circular blue bioeconomy has the potential to improve the efficient use of aquatic resources but also to contribute to the bioeconomy and the circular economy at large as improvements can have cascading effects on other major industries. The study proposes targeted recommendations for improved policy and strategy options.

Selected findings from the stakeholder activities (interviews, focus groups) are shown in Figure 5. The pie chart indicates how frequently certain topics emerged in the different theme categories. The resource and regulatory issues dominated the discussion in both countries.

¹⁶ Nína María Saviolidis*, Guðrún Ólafsdóttir & Sigurður Bogason (2023). Barriers to a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland, webinar arranged by an NKJ co-funded network “What do sustainable agro-marine food systems mean in different Nordic contexts?” June 14th, 2023 Nordic Joint Committee for Agricultural and Food Research

¹⁷ Nína M. Saviolidis*, Guðrún Ólafsdóttir, Magnus Stoud Myhre, Andrea Viken Strand & Shraddha Mehta (2023) Drivers and barriers for the advancement of a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland and Norway. International Conference on Resource Sustainability (icRS 2023) August 7-9th 2023, University of Surrey, UK.

In Iceland one of the major issues that emerged is the need for mapping all waste streams both in terms of quantities but also in terms of the content and quality of these streams.

Figure 5 Summary and selected findings from stakeholder interviews on the perception of challenges and barriers in Iceland and Norway (Adapted from Saviolidis et al. 2023)

Similar to previous research, **access to and the quality of the raw material** was an issue that was mentioned by many of the participants. A couple of issues are related to this: the increase in price for raw material (can be a challenge but is also a sign of the increased value of raw material), and the amount of rest raw material that goes to feed production vs food and other value-added activities. While in a business perspective it makes sense to move higher in the value pyramid from feed to food, the ethical point of view was also addressed in the interviews in relation to a world demanding more food/proteins. The drivers, challenges, enablers, and barriers of circular economy transition and their relationships have been investigated in a wide range of previous studies (Kirchherr et al., 2018¹⁸; Van Keulen

¹⁸ Kirchherr, J., Piscicelli, L., Bour, R., Kostense-Smit, E., Muller, J., Huibrechtse-Truijens, A., Hekkert, M., 2018. Barriers to the circular economy: evidence from the European Union (EU). *J. Ecol. Econ.* 150, 264–272.

and Kirchherr, 2021¹⁹; Oanh Thi-Kieu Ho et al. (2023)¹. If challenges are not overcome, they can become barriers which hinder the movement toward circularity. The earlier studies have highlighted the importance of “using drivers to tackle challenges and crystallise them into enablers for the CE transition”¹. Our findings from the interviews identified **technological innovation as a driver for transition** for example, in aquaculture, the new production systems, offshore, land based and closed systems are innovations that may solve some of the challenges (sea lice, escape, loss of biodiversity) of the traditional sea cage systems. Similar, insights into the drivers and barriers to the transition towards sustainability and transition pathways for the farmed salmon value chain were reported by Gudbrandsdottir et al. (2021)²⁰. **Circularity, sustainable feed, and new production system** like land-based operation were identified as drivers or niches that could influence the transition of the current system (regime). The multi-level perspective (MLP) framework and the global value chain (GVC) governance framework were applied to explore the interactions that occur in and between three main analytical levels: (a) landscape (influenced by heterogeneous factors e.g., commodity prices, cultural values, environmental problems), (b) regime (the current food system) and, (c) niche-innovations^{21, 22}. Transitions according to the MLP refer to changes in dominant regimes often resulting from landscape pressures and the emergence of niches which can be technological, social, or institutional. **Policymakers, managers and other actors can promote and enable a sustainability transition of the current food system** while incumbent actors with vested interest may use their power to resist system change²⁰.

Integrated policy was also mentioned in several interviews as an enabler or driver of more sustainable fisheries and aquaculture supply chains. A holistic territorial / national approach is needed to establish sustainability goals and targets, while **considering the overall food system. Infrastructure** was also discussed, especially in terms of **waste and wastewater management**. What to do with waste from e.g., collagen production (a value-added activity) and what about sludge from the aquaculture industry. **Energy supply** issues were also discussed. There are synergies in establishing infrastructure for enhanced circular bioeconomy as part of the food system, including waste and wastewater management as well as **logistics optimisation for efficient transportation** when sourcing raw materials and distribution of products to market with the aim to minimise waste and ensure quality of products. Since **FLW are largely caused at the intersection between different actors of the food value chain**, it is important to adopt a food systems perspective including all sectors of the food value chain (Fritche et al., 2020 p40), and including retail and households.

In terms of **regulatory issues**, some of the topics that emerged in the interviews were: **lack of institutional capacity, the need for common standards and metrics, the need for long term policies** that can survive through different political 4yr terms and the need to integrate policy objectives so that different policies align with each other. Figure 6 shows the conceptual circular blue bioeconomy framework integrated with the issues that have been raised in the interviews. The important factors related to **resource use, regulatory, market and social aspects** are highlighted in the boxes (outlined yellow). The factors are both enabling conditions and challenges to be addressed, such as **environmental impacts** that need to be reduced and/or addressed. The results from the interviews and focus groups will be elaborated in a scientific publication.

¹⁹ Van Keulen, M., Kirchherr, J., 2021. The implementation of the circular economy: barriers and enablers in the coffee value chain. *J. Clean. Prod.* 281, 125033.

²⁰ Gudbrandsdottir, I.Y.; Saviolidis, N.M.; Olafsdottir, G.; Oddsson, G.V.; Stefansson, H.; Bogason, S.G. Transition Pathways for the Farmed Salmon Value Chain: Industry Perspectives and Sustainability Implications. *Sustainability* **2021**, *13*, 12106

²¹ Geels, F.W.; Schot, J. Typology of sociotechnical transition pathways. *Res. Policy* **2007**, *36*, 399–417

²² Geels, F.W. The multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions: Responses to seven criticisms. *Environ. Innov. Soc. Transit.* **2011**, *1*, 24–40.

4. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

The objective of task T3.2 *Stakeholder engagement* was to engage stakeholders for consultation on the selected indicators from T3.1 and assess their willingness to share data and assessment results for enhanced transparency and circularity. As companies are already reporting their sustainability performance and utilising common frameworks and established indicators in their CSR reports in line with the selected set of indicators reported in D3.1, the approach for the stakeholder activities /workshops in T3.2 was revised towards in-depth interviews and focus groups rather than workshops as reported herein (D3.2).

The findings show that realising the potential of a more circular blue bioeconomy requires the development of target-based overarching strategies and the implementation of a systemic approach cutting across different sectors (e.g., agriculture, tourism, transport, and energy sector). A transition towards a circular economy for the blue bioeconomy can contribute to resource efficiency gains which are integral to sustainable development. At the same time, it can also stimulate increased profit by turning waste streams or lower value products into value or higher value streams. Advancing the circular blue bioeconomy can also contribute to internationally agreed upon goals: the SDGs.

But there are trade-offs to consider, and assessments are necessary for more explicit evaluation of sustainability trade-offs for example with regards to rural development issues and the principle of food first. Perhaps what is primarily needed is very accurate accounting of “waste” / rest raw materials and other materials streams. Apart from some R&D investments, development of the bioeconomy is mainly left to the market which can sometimes undermine broader sustainability goals so it’s important to critically assess policies and strategies and whether they are synergistic or not.

Content analysis of CSR reports will be the focus of the work in the Bluebio Cofunded top-up project Smartchain_policy. The aim is to extend the Smartchain project’s work on sustainability indicators by analysing company reports from Iceland and Norway to investigate what targets the private sector has set and how it measures its performance in achieving those targets (which specific metrics do companies use). This research activity will extend the Smartchain project’s tasks on sustainability indicators, data availability and transparency through the systematic analysis of reporting and standards. The investigation will be conducted through a qualitative content analysis of companies’ sustainability reports using the software MAXQDA.

Further work in Task 3.3. *Governance of blue bioeconomy supply chains and scenario for innovative business models* will focus on the role of governance, policy, and supply chain actors to promote improvements and guide policy making. Assessment of synergies and trade-offs among the different sustainability dimensions and performance targets against circularity and sustainability criteria will be evaluated. Thresholds will be defined either through targets based on national-level policy targets or sectoral level targets (where available) using trend-based assessment where well-defined thresholds are not available.

The governance and policy dynamics of blue bioeconomy value chains and sectors will be evidenced from the ground level of policy implementation regarding circularity strategies and regulation and drawing from results of the interviews (T3.2) conducted with seafood industry, policy officials and other stakeholders in Iceland and Norway. The process will elicit their experiences through identifying current challenges and gaps, and which further policy actions can address, improve, and enhance the innovation environment. The governance aspects include for example the market and supply chain structures, social aspects, power, and

information asymmetries amongst value chain actors, and how collaboration and sharing of information is best achieved. *D3.3 Key leverage points and role of actors (M36).*

Advancing the circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland and Norway

Case study 3: Circularity in the blue bioeconomy value chain: With important sustainability challenges emerging for seafood business, multidimensional indicators to monitor sustainability status and improvement potentials are crucial, while also considering governance and policy implications. Collaboration across borders to establish well working networks throughout the value chains can be a part of the solution to fulfil the transition to the blue circular economy. The mapping of seafood supply chains in WP1 was the first step in the SMARTCHAIN project to identify hotspots regarding rest raw materials and food loss and waste. The case study enables research and supports activities in all WPs where WP3 specifically focuses on sustainability criteria and circular economy objectives in the bioeconomy value chains in Norway and Iceland. The work benefits from collaboration with the industry partner BRIM in Iceland, as a Living lab providing access and insight to the company's current practices. Scenarios for circular system models and simulations will be elaborated in WP5 and linked to master students' thesis work at DTU.

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ANNEX I FOOD LOSS & FOOD WASTE

Figure 1: Stages in a generic seafood supply chain where food loss, rest raw materials and food waste occur

From Mehta et al. (2022)⁶.

Figure 4 Categorization of the different fractions of FLW and RRM for further application

From: Mehta, S., Myhre, M., Olafsdottir, G., Iordan, C.M., Thakur, M. (2022). Resource utilization in seafood supply chains: Food loss, food waste and rest raw materials. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D1.1 & D1.2, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 48 pages

ANNEX II MATERIAL AND INFORMATION FLOWS MODELLING TECHNIQUE (MIFMT).

From Strand et al. 2023. Manuscript submitted for publication Based on SMARTCHAIN D1.4. Figure 3: Conceptual model of the fishery supply chain in Norway and Iceland based on the MIFMT method including harvest, landing, processing of primary product, processing of RRM, transport and storage and Retail.

ANNEX III CONCEPT NOTE FOR INTERVIEWS

CONCEPT NOTE

SMARTCHAIN - SMART SOLUTIONS FOR ADVANCING SUPPLY SYSTEMS IN BLUE BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAINS

As part of the Green Deal, the European Commission has adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan to promote circular economy processes, sustainable consumption, and more efficient use of resources (COM, 2020). The circular economy paradigm calls for the redesign of the linear economic system whereby the environmental and social costs of products are externalized, to a circular system based on closed-loop resource flows that can preserve the embedded environmental and economic value in products over time. It is a way to increase resource efficiency by intentionally narrowing, slowing, and closing materials and energy flows (Pieroni et al., 2019).

To achieve these aims companies will need to reconsider their value creation and adopt strategies that promote circular economy objectives such as reuse, repair, or remanufacturing. The concept of a circular business model has been developed to advance these objectives. A circular business model is a way for companies to create, deliver and capture value in ways that both advance circular economy objectives but also improve the sustainability performance of organizations and provide competitive advantage. Some strategies for circular business models can be realised at the firm level but others will likely require multi-firm and multi-actor collaborations for business model alignment (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018).

SMARTCHAIN focuses on circular economy solutions for the blue bioeconomy. The bioeconomy "is the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy" (COM, 2019, p. 8). The blue bioeconomy emphasizes aquatic or marine environments, and involves a specific focus on novel applications, including non-food, food, and feed. The blue bioeconomy includes both primary and secondary activities and other sectors may be connected to the blue bioeconomy through their services to bioeconomic activities (Nordic Council, 2014).

A transition towards a circular economy for the blue bioeconomy can contribute to resource efficiency gains which are integral to sustainable development. The blue bioeconomy needs to follow the principles of sustainable development such that it contributes to meeting the needs of present generations without compromising the needs of future generations through a focus on the three main pillars of sustainability: economic, social, and environmental (Fritsche et al., 2020). Blue bioeconomy development can support the achievement of broad societal goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through an emphasis on sustainability, circularity, and innovative approaches.

ADVANCING THE CIRCULAR BLUE BIOECONOMY IN ICELAND AND NORWAY

In the context of the SMARTCHAIN project, the general aim is to develop approaches and tools for sustainable utilisation, production planning, logistics optimisation, and traceability to facilitate transfer of bio-resources from catch/production throughout the value chain of fisheries and aquaculture products. Furthermore, SMARTCHAIN will explore the perceptions of companies, experts and policy makers in Iceland and Norway to gauge the ways in which they contribute to the circular bioeconomy. The goal is to elucidate the opportunities and challenges for further advancement of circular blue bioeconomy strategies.

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ANNEX IV DESCRIPTIVES - INTERVIEWS

Pseudonym & National context	Type	Role of participant	Date taken	Interview	Focus group
IS-FG1	Aquaculture company	CFO	May 21		#1
IS-FG1	Aquaculture company	CEO	May 21		#1
IS-FG1	Aquaculture company	CEO	May 21		#1
IS-FG2	Aquaculture company	Project & quality manager	May 21		#2
IS-FG2	Public institution	Expert	May 21		#2
IS-FG2	Aquaculture company	CEO	May 21		#2
IS-FG2	Aquaculture company	CEO	May 21		#2
IS1	Shipbuilding	Technical and marketing manager	May 22	#1	
IS2	Packaging	Research manager	May 22	#2	
IS3	IT	CEO	May 22	#3	
IS4	Biotech	CEO	May 22	#4	
IS5	Packaging (start-up)	Research Manager	June 22	#5	
IS6	Energy NGO	Project manager	June 22	#6	
IS7	Biotech	Managing director	June 22	#7	
IS8	Fishing company	Chief Innovation Officer	Oct 22	#8	
IS9	Equipment	Research Scientist	Feb23	#9	
NO1	Funding agency & Research Institution	R&D director & Expert	May 21	#10	
NO2	Aquaculture company	CFO	June 21	#11	
NO3	Aquaculture company	Community Relations Officer	June 21	#12	
NO4	Aquaculture company	CEO	June 21	#13	
NO5	Biotech	CCO	Aug 22	#14	
NO6	Packaging	Sustainability Manager	Dec22	#15	
NO7	Food corp./ingredients	Sustainability manager & Supplier development manager	Jan23	#16	
NO8	Equipment	Chief Sustainability Officer	Feb23	#17	
EU1	Public institution	Polymaker	June 21	#18	

ANNEX V. CSR REPORTING (ICELAND)

Table 1 List of the largest fisheries companies in Iceland according to catch volumes (Aflamark) in 2022-2023 and information on sustainability reporting and certifications from their websites.

Company	Website /info	Sustainability report /year first published	Guidelines	SFS Policy signed	Certifications* and memberships (Initiatives)
Síldarvinnslan hf. SVN	IS	Yes / 2019	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC, Global TRUST (IFFO), IRF, FEMAS (feed material assurance), Tún /Naturland (organic), GFSI (BRC)
Brim hf	IS/EN	Yes / 2017	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC, IRF, GSSI
Ísfélag hf. (Rammi)	IS/EN	YES /2021	GRI	Yes	Global TRUST, MSC, HACCP, FEMAS, TÚN organic
Samherji Ísland ehf	IS/EN	No	N/A	Yes	MSC, IRF, BRC, GFSI, BAP
Vinnslustöðin hf. Huginn	IS/EN	No	N/A	No Yes	MSC, IRF , HACCP
Eskja hf.	IS/EN	YES / EN 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC; Equal pay ÍST85:2012: IFFO&FEMAS, Tún organic production
Skinney-Pinganes hf.	IS/EN	YES / IS 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	Gender equality ÍST85:2012: IFS/GFSI; MSC; IFFO&FEMAS
Gjögur hf.	No	No	N/A	Yes	MSC
Loðnuvinnslan hf.	IS	No	N/A	Yes	MSC, Gender Equal pay IST 85:2012
FISK Seafood ehf.	IS/EN	Yes / IS 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	IFS, MSC, IRF, Equal pay ÍST85:2012
Thorfish (Þorbjörn hf.)	IS	Yes / IS 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC IRF, ISF
Nesfiskur ehf.	IS	No	N/A	Yes	MSC Gender equal pay ÍST85:2012
Hraðfrystihúsið - Gunnvör hf.	IS/EN	No	N/A	Yes	IRF
Útgerðarfélag Reykjavíkur hf	EN	No (public financial statements)	N/A	Yes	MSC, IRF
Vísir hf (Síldarvinnslan)	IS	YES /IS / 2020	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC, IRF,BRC Equal pay ÍST 85:2012, Long line caught

Sustainability reports are prepared in accordance with the GRI Standard (Global Reporting Initiative GRI) and **SFS sustainability policy** based on the UN SDGs, ESG reporting guide 2.0 (Fisheries Iceland and Nasdaq's ESG guidelines, translated to Icelandic)

- Certifications are not all listed on the websites, e.g. MSC certification verified on www.msc.org

The figures show the list of the largest fisheries companies according to catch volumes (Aflamark), type of species and landing location. On top are all species where the volumes of pelagics dominate, while volumes of demersal species are shown below. Source: Fiskistofa, 2023.

The fisheries in Iceland are characterised by integrated companies with ownership of a large share of the fishing quota. The fishing fleet consists of 1 549 vessels (in 2021), thereof 41 trawlers, 693 decked vessels and 815 undecked boats (Statistics Iceland, 2023a). The total catch of all species landed in Iceland in 2021 was about 1 153 million tonnes (round weight) (Statistics Iceland, 2023b). Atlantic cod and pelagic species (herring, capelin, blue whiting, and mackerel) are the most important species in terms of volume landed. Cod landings were about 271 000 tonnes while total landings of pelagics was about 655 000 tonnes (Statistics Iceland, 2023c). (From D 1.3)